

Acknowledgement

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Effect of Temperature on the Rate of Coagulation of Ferric Tellurate, Chromium Tellurate and Vanadium Pentaoxide Hydrosols by Viscometric Technique

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RECENTLY, Ghosh and coworkers have studied the effect of temperature on the coagulation of thorium oxide and ceric oxide hydrosols and have interpreted their results with the help of an equation, relating time of slow coagulation (t_s) and temperature, based on the theory of stability of colloids developed by Fuchs², Derjaguin³ and Overbeek⁴.

The equation derived is

$$\log t_s = \frac{N(E + V_{max})}{2.303 RT} + B \quad (1)$$

From equation (1) it is clear that a plot $\log t_s$ against $1/T$ should give a straight line.

In this communication an attempt has been made to verify this equation and thereby obtain the maximum value of the potential energy barrier, V_{max} , for the coagulation of ferric tellurate, chromium tellurate and vanadium pentaoxide hydrosols.

Experimental

(a) Preparation of sols :

Positively charged hydrosols of ferric tellurate and chromium tellurate were prepared, according to the method reported in our earlier publication⁵, and were subsequently dialysed.

Negatively charged vanadium pentaoxide hydrosol was prepared by treating about 15 g. ammonium vanadate with 15 ml Conc. HNO_3 in a porcelain basin with constant stirring. The precipitate so formed was then filtered off and well washed with water till the dark red sludge began to give red colour in the filtrate. The precipitate was then transferred to a conical flask and was shaken in a litre of water to convert it into a dark red coloured sol, which was subjected to dialysis.

(b) Determination of rate of coagulation :

The rate of coagulation of the sols was determined viscometrically. Viscosity measurements were made by Scarpa's method⁶ modified by Farrow⁷ and improved by Prasad and coworkers⁸. The temperature was controlled using a Gallenkamp thermostat. The progress of coagulation was detected by recording changes in viscosity. The sol and the electrolyte were taken in a number of viscometers placed simultaneously in the thermostated bath. After a desired interval of time the viscosity of the coagulating system was found out in one viscometer and at the subsequent interval in the other viscometer and so on. This was done only to avoid the disturbances in the system during the process of coagulation. However, the uncertainties involved in viscosity measurement cannot be ruled out. For each set of observations 5 ml of a mixture of water and electrolyte of known concentration was added to 5 ml of the sol (total volume being 10 ml in each case) and the viscosity was determined at different intervals. Several sets of observations were taken with different concentrations of coagulating electrolyte, but the concentrations of the electrolyte were so adjusted that the time of coagulation was of the order of 5 to 80 minutes. This was considered as the time of slow coagulation. The whole process was repeated at different temperatures. The relative change of viscosity was determined by the ratio $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$ where η_0 is the initial viscosity and η is the viscosity at the end of the interval time t' . This ratio was taken according to Freundlich⁹ and Gann¹⁰ as a measure of relative increase in coagulation.

The points of inflexion in the curves obtained by plotting $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$ (i.e., degree of coagulation, x) against time were

taken to denote same stage of coagulation ($\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = 0$)

brought about by adding different concentrations of the electrolyte. The times corresponding to points of inflexion were taken as the times¹¹ of slow coagulation corresponding to a definite stage of coagulation.

Results and Discussion

The relative changes of viscosity i.e., $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$ during slow coagulation of ferric tellurate sol in the presence of $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$ have been plotted against time (Fig. 1) at different temperatures. Similar figures were obtained with other sols. For ferric tellurate and chromium tellurate sols the experiments were carried out at 20°, 30°, 40°, and 50°. For chromium tellurate sol the electrolyte used was $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$. The coagulation of vanadium pentaoxide sol was studied in the presence of $5.6 \times 10^{-4} M BaCl_2$ at 25°, 35°, 45° and 55°.

Fig. 1. Coagulation of Ferric Tellurate Sol at different temperatures with $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$.

The logarithm of time of slow coagulation ($\log t_s$) has been plotted against $1/T$ for each of the sols studied (Fig. 2). All the plots have yielded straight lines

Fig. 2. $\log t_s$ Vs $1/T$.

confirming the validity of the equation (1).

The value of NV_{max} for ferric tellurate sol in the presence of $1.4 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$ is calculated from the slope of the plot. This is equal to 9356 cal., the value of $N E$ for water being 3305 cal./mole¹². Similarly for chromium tellurate sol in the presence of $1.2 \times 10^{-3} M K_2SO_4$ the value of $N V_{max}$ has been found to be 10285 cal., and for vanadium pentaoxide sol in the presence of $5.6 \times 10^{-4} M BaCl_2$ this has been found to be 8495 cal.

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Condensation of Deoxybenzoin with Aldehydes

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THE present investigation deals with the condensation of deoxybenzoin with a number of aldehydes in Knoevenagel's reaction. The identity of the products were established on the basis of analysis and IR absorption spectrum (Table 1).